

A GSFC Perspective on the Execution of Faster, Better, Cheaper

Jim Watzin¹
NASA Goddard Space Flight Center
Code 410.3, Bldg. 10, Room 201A
Greenbelt, Maryland 20771
301-286-7417
jim.watzin@gsfc.nasa.gov

Abstract—The Small Explorer (SMEX) Project at NASA Goddard Space Flight Center (GSFC) has accumulated nearly a decade of experience building missions with the underlying philosophy of “Faster, Better, Cheaper” (FBC). Four satellites are now successfully operating on orbit and one more will be launched by the time this paper is presented. Additionally, this project, under the Explorer Technology Infusion effort, has developed a protoflight version of a 21st Century FBC spacecraft bus that has just completed environmental qualification and has been selected as the base spacecraft for NASA’s Triana mission. Design and production of these six high performance spacecraft, in just ten years time, has provided a unique base of experience from which to draw lessons learned. This paper will discuss the fundamental practices that have been used by the SMEX Project as well as relevant experiences from other innovative projects at GSFC.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION
2. ENABLING PRINCIPLES
3. PROJECT CHARACTERISTICS
4. TECHNICAL PRACTICES
5. INSTITUTIONAL MANAGEMENT CHARACTERISTICS
6. CONCLUSION
7. REFERENCES
8. BIOGRAPHY

1. INTRODUCTION

GSFC has had nearly a decade of experience in executing unique, highly specialized science missions under the NASA FBC shifts in program structure. Several missions, notably the SMEX missions SAMPEX, FAST, SWAS, and TRACE and the EESP mission TOMS, have been successfully launched and are demonstrating excellent performance on-orbit. Many others, such as the SMEX mission WIRE, and the SMEX-Lite technology initiative, the Explorer mission FUSE, the EESP VCL mission, and the Mid-Explorer MAP mission, are in advanced stages of development. Each of these programs has been managed by different organizations with considerable variations in civil

servant and contractor involvement. All, however, have been executed with remarkably similar values and philosophies. This paper captures the principles found to be significant to the success of these efforts.

All programs have found that FBC requires a focus on competence, empowerment with responsibility, freedom to innovate outside the established norms, and constant situational awareness. FBC is, in short, a philosophy, a mechanism of sorts to promote creativity and responsibility on the part of the mission teams conducting NASA’s science missions. The paradigm shift lies in the fact that the team establishes its own processes and practices, ones that are best suited for the team members involved, rather than allow the institutional process to impose its methodologies. This shift encourages the team to take full ownership of, and responsibility for the project, in turn promoting an environment of commitment and loyalty that binds the team together. The team thrives knowing that its decisions will determine mission success or failure. To succeed within these new freedoms, the project must recruit self-motivated, talented personnel; individuals with keen technical and communication skills to fill all key positions. This team make-up, in turn, thrives on the personal ownership and empowered responsibility they have been granted, carrying the project through its activities. The project must carefully, and continually, assess the skills and limitations of its team members, shifting and adjusting roles and responsibilities to best utilize everyone’s talent. Care must be taken to pair less experienced personnel with those capable of mentoring them such that all parties benefit. The institutional organization must be flexible enough to recognize that not all people can thrive in this environment and be willing to reassign personnel to more appropriate assignments if necessary.

The project provides a focus for the team, setting guidelines and requirements that are based heavily on both customer desires and feedback from the team. The project’s role is to encourage the challenging and definitization of all requirements, to make timely decisions consistent with the mission and the evolving character of the team, and to facilitate effective communication between the customer and the implementing team. It is a team-driven process, not a process-driven team. Our FBC experience has avoided the pitfalls so eloquently summarized by Robert A. Frosch, former NASA Administrator and Assistant Secretary of the Navy, who commented on the failure of organizations to

¹U.S. Government work not protected by U.S. copyright.”

produce successful missions; “I believe that the fundamental difficulty is that we have all become so entranced with technique that we think entirely in terms of procedures, systems, milestone charts, PERT diagrams, reliability systems, configuration management, maintain-ability groups, and the other minor paper tools of the ‘system engineers’ and manager. We have forgotten that someone must be in control and must exercise personal management, knowledge, and understanding to create a system. As a result, we have developments that follow all of the rules, but fail.”² FBC Projects thrive on the personal ownership that the team takes of its mission.

Each of the GSFC FBC implementations have put someone clearly in charge and granted the teams the freedom to exercise personal skill and judgment in developing their mission. The institution, in turn, has provided a reservoir of skills, knowledge, and facilities that could be readily called upon when needed by the team. The independence of the team coupled with the ready reserve of the larger institution (GSFC, Applied Physics Laboratory (APL), etc.) in standby has been key to our successes. The ability to call upon the depth of resources when the team determines it needs assistance as opposed to the institution “loading the team” is a critical shift in paradigm. The institution must be willing to empower and trust the team that has been chosen to execute their project. Excessive review and oversight greatly slows the pace of any team and greatly diminishes its decision-making capability.

The key principles and values used by the GSFC in conducting FBC missions can be summarized in the following four fundamental areas:

2. ENABLING PRINCIPLES

True Empowerment of the Team

The institution must relinquish control to the project team it has chosen. It must not “overmanage” the project. Micromanagement is fatal to FBC. A clear, concise project plan can be useful to definitize the control that the project has been given.

Freedom to Innovate Outside Traditional Institutional Norms and Practices

The institution needs to allow its team the freedom to search for *better* ways to complete its work than what the established institution has accomplished in the past. Blind adherence to institutional process reduces the motivation of the team to really “think things out” as would be optimum for their application. It effectively dilutes its sense of responsibility. Institutional norms should be the basis for departure, not a mandatory requirement.

Clear Accountability of the Project for Mission Success

The project team must know that “the buck stops here” in terms of responsibility for mission success. The institution must be clear in defining to the project the level of acceptable risk. The project, not the institution, must then manage the activity.

Acceptance of Reasonable Risk

No real progress is ever made without risk. The project team cannot “push the envelope” if the institution or the customer is overly concerned about failure. Prudent risk-taking should be rewarded, not punished. Fundamental risk related guidelines should be spelled out in the beginning of the project. All parties involved need to be aware of them.

Inherent Requirements Flexibility (Designs are not Overspecified)

With short, fixed schedules and cost-capped funding, the only relief the project team has is the requirements. The team must be allowed to trade and adjust requirements as long as the “goals” of the mission are met. In fact, the project team must be “continuously rescoping” the mission, to effectively deal with the myriad of problems and trade-offs that arise during the mission development. In this fashion, teams can meet the intent of the mission, seldom ever needing to truly “descope”. Small, frequent, minor changes are much more effective than large, discontinuous single changes in maintaining the progress of the mission team. This flexibility, when pushed down to the lowest levels of decision-making, is a powerful mechanism in maintaining the integrity of a FBC mission. The Principal Investigator (PI) must be actively enrolled in the team to accomplish this. Traditional boilerplate specifications need to be replaced with only the driving requirements. The subsystems must feel that they, in large measure, are the owners of their system requirements. Like the PI and systems engineer, they must be allowed the freedom to negotiate and adjust their specifications, provided that they meet mission performance needs. Overspecification generates extra work and excessive margins. The systems engineer and lead engineers must always be aware of their margins and prudently dispense them to meet cost and schedule. Losing those margins in overspecified designs is wasteful.

Design to Cost (Hard Cost Caps)

True, hard cost caps force design and process trades to be made in a timely manner. Given just one more day and one more dollar, any engineer can make it better. The project must learn to recognize when good enough is enough. Unlimited funding promotes an unlimited design phase. It’s that simple!

3. PROJECT CHARACTERISTICS

Principal Investigator Focused Team

To work effectively within this tightly resource constrained environment the PI must interact with the team so that the trades and implications of the mission requirements are well understood. The PI must work to ensure that the goals of the mission are achieved in balance with resource limitations.

Agile, Balanced Project Management

Effective project management begins with the recognition and respect of the development team. With a strong, competent technical team, it is unnecessary for project management to mandate or direct the technical development of the project rather; it should focus on motivation and communication. Strong systems engineering, so critical to a FBC mission, enables project management to become part of the team, contributing ideas at a higher level to stimulate the team's problem-solving capabilities. Project management must encourage timely decisions and know when intervention is required to maintain the cost, schedule, and risk set forth by upper management. It cannot be emphasized strongly enough that to operate *faster*, the project must be innovative, flexible, and responsive to the needs of the team. Incorrect decisions can be corrected, but late decisions will stifle progress terribly. Management's role is to facilitate the progress of the team. By helping to develop clear plans and guiding the team through the business aspects of the mission, management is complementary to the systems engineering effort, providing a true resource for the team. Management leads by facilitating, coordinating, and encouraging effective communication rather than directing.

Strong Systems Engineering

Strong systems engineering is absolutely critical to leading a fast-paced technical team. The systems engineer must take technical ownership of the mission and guide the multitude of development decisions accordingly. He must promote discussion and trades amongst all subsystems involved in the mission. Thorough up-front systems definition activities should be conducted by the core team prior to fully staffing the design and development teams.

Dedicated Lead Engineers with "Systems Perspective"

Lead engineers must work from a perspective of "what is best for the overall mission" and not get trapped in optimizing "pieceparts." Sub-system tunnel vision limits the flexibility and responsiveness of the team.

Decision-Making at the Lowest Possible Level

The lead engineers must be considered part of the project and empowered to make decisions within their area of responsibility. Well-structured, *mutually developed* schedules, spending plans, technical requirements, and interfaces enable effective distributed decision-making.

Active Principal Investigators with Hardware Experience

Theoreticians are poorly prepared to appreciate the many, subtle trades and decisions required to build hardware. For a PI to effectively lead the team he must have a sense of the work at hand. A PI would be wise to employ an experienced technical manager.

Minimal Documentation: Document only when Value is Added and to Facilitate Communication

Don't document just "for the record" or the obvious. Requirements, system specification and interfaces, user guides, and implementation plans are key, fundamental documents.

Compressed Schedule

Constrained schedules, like budgets, force trade-offs. More than just a plan to be tracked, the schedule must be aggressively and dynamically managed to optimize team performance. It must be a living document that is continuously adjusted to account for an ever-changing, unpredictable environment. The Project Manager must be vigilant, developing a team awareness of the impact of all deviations to the baseline plan.

Partner-Type Relationship with Vendors

Vendors don't share the goals or urgency of the project team unless they are enrolled as partners. Treated simply as suppliers, they will make decisions based on their company profits and not your need.

4. TECHNICAL PRACTICES

Single-String Designs

The inherent simplicity of single-string designs greatly reduces cost and schedule. The additional engineering and testing required for system redundancy increases nearly exponentially over that necessary to develop single-string designs. Quite often the more complex, redundant designs are only marginally more likely to complete the mission than a well-prepared, thoroughly tested single string system.

Single, robust designs that minimize the EEE parts count, if built with 'good parts' and well tested have extremely high probabilities of long life. KISS (Keep It Simple, Stupid!) really is a meaningful design strategy, not just a cliché.

Heavy Dependence on Modern (but Mature) Technologies

Modern technologies are necessary to achieve the high performance required of the new "small-sats", but to meet the cost and schedule constraints these technologies must be reasonably mature, well beyond the laboratory stage of development. All that can be afforded is fundamental engineering. Research and Development (R&D) efforts cannot be effectively rushed to flight on an FBC operational mission.

Heavy Dependence on "Smart Spacecraft"

Smart spacecraft greatly simplify the ground segment of a space mission, reducing system complexity, facility, and long-term personnel requirements. They also boost mission reliability by minimizing the effects of human error in operations. Smart spacecraft need not be complex. Emphasis should be on simple and practical safing strategies and on operational simplification features. Fault detection algorithms should look for 'final effects' (i.e., low battery state-of-charge, etc.³) rather than root cause, triggering spacecraft default into a minimalistic survival mode. Leave complex troubleshooting to the engineers on the ground. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is still far from being a mature, cost effective, technology for most flight missions, particularly single string missions.

Standardized Interfaces

Well-defined interfaces enable many of the development efforts to proceed in parallel. Use of standard interfaces eliminates a substantial amount of engineering effort that, in the past, had gone into designing and maturing the custom interfaces. Use of commercial, standard interfaces leverages many industry efforts, providing economical access to well debugged test equipment and parts.

Tailored Test Programs Focusing on Extensive Systems Testing

Mission test programs must be tailored to stress the mission system being developed. The system is most complex when fully assembled and consequently should be heavily tested in that configuration. Cost/schedule risk trades can be made that migrate subsystem testing to system testing in order to facilitate earlier deliveries. Environmental test requirements should be representative of the mission environment. Care should be taken to define reasonable test margins.

High Quality Parts Qualification Program

Good parts minimize disruptive test failures late in the development cycle and improve probability of mission success. Though many lower quality parts can indeed be flown, consistency from part-to-part is always in question. Custom screening processes and qualification tests must be established to validate those parts. No single parts control program is right for every project. Tailoring the project's approach towards qualifying the parts is key to achieving an appropriate balance between part test, system test, cost, and schedule.

Less Formal Reviews, More Peer Reviews

Peer reviews reveal more substantial design issues than formal, general reviews. The increased technical knowledge of the reviewers coupled with the more relaxed environment for the team member being reviewed provides for a more effective process.

Co-Located Teams

Co-location exponentially increases the speed and quality of team communication. Full co-location of all disciplines (management, design, test, and operations) from the inception of the project through completion fosters true concurrent engineering where the early design can be effectively influenced by the implementers and end users. The level of co-location needed varies from project-to-project and is somewhat dependent on the skills and background of the individual team members. Often it is more effective to just co-locate the subsystem leads, leaving their unit designers with the parent product centers where they have access to additional peer support and technical tools.

Integrated Development and Operations Team

Integrating all aspects of the mission allows for better systems engineering and quicker and more efficient transfer through the mission phases.

5. INSTITUTIONAL MANAGEMENT CHARACTERISTICS

It is incumbent upon the institution that sponsors an FBC project to not only provide, but also maintain and foster, an environment in which the project will thrive. Institutional management must set the priority of the project and work to ensure that it is getting the support it needs to conduct its mission. For this to happen effectively, the project must earn the confidence of management and management, in turn, must be responsive to project needs. In a team driven process, institutional management must be enlightened to entrust its teams to properly execute their missions. It must focus on ensuring that the projects have the resources and

talent necessary to do their jobs and avoid the natural temptation to direct them in how to accomplish their jobs. Effective communication is key to this process. GSFC has been experimenting with different variations of management technique and format over the past several years, some more successful than others. A hybrid of these approaches appears to be most effective for FBC missions. Structured formal management reviews, unstructured routine management reviews, and regular casual management interactions comprise this hybrid approach, all serving a valuable role in establishing and maintaining a good management/project relationship.

Formal Reviews—Structured formal reviews serve to provide management with insight into the overall, big picture health of the project (i.e., cost, schedule, and major problems). These reviews, if properly conducted, not only inform management of project status but encourage the project to stand back from the routine of daily problems and take stock of its own progress, reviewing not only its accomplishments but also reassessing its future needs. The review should be comprehensive enough so as to require considerable effort on the part of the project to prepare. To be effective, this type of review must be held frequently enough to allow meaningful corrections to be implemented but not so frequently as to encourage micro-management of the project by the institution. On a three-year development effort, these reviews should occur approximately twice a year.

Unstructured Reviews—Unstructured routine reviews serve to give management insight into the progress of the project. It is best left unstructured so as to allow the project to address any issue that “it deems necessary to get attention” is surfaced and addressed in appropriate depth by whoever in the project team is best suited to the discussion. This format allows for more interactions between management and the project team. The intent of these reviews is to help management develop a sense for the nature of the project development and to assess its (the institution’s) effectiveness in supporting the project. The emphasis of these reviews should be to provide background and context information to management – they must not become a forum for the institution to attempt to manage the project. To be effective, they should be held regularly – on the average of once per month and should take relatively little effort by the project to prepare.

Management—Regular casual management interactions are key to building the trust of the institution to empower the project. Management has a need to feel that the project is making decisions consistent with the values of the institution. To best gain that confidence it must have a window into the decision-making process of the project team. That insight is usually not obtainable through the status reviews. Additionally, the project needs access to management experience and insight, to seek advice on matters that elude the project’s sphere of influence. These needs are best met by regular casual interaction between the Project Manager and principal Institutional Manager responsible for the project’s activities. These should consist of short, regularly scheduled meetings where any subject

can be discussed, as well as “walk-arounds” of management in the project work environment. Meeting the people, seeing the work, and understanding the values and characteristics of the project is key to management gaining confidence in its team. Secure with that confidence, management can avoid the temptation to second guess and micromanage, having balanced its need to know with the project’s need to control.

6. CONCLUSION

All four characteristic elements of these FBC practices, the *ENABLING PRINCIPLES*, *PROJECT CHARACTERISTICS*, *TECHNICAL PRACTICES*, and *INSTITUTIONAL MANAGEMENT CHARACTERISTICS* are equally important, each supporting the others in accomplishing mission success. Competent judgment that balances technical risk and knowledge of team members skill is the glue that binds it all together. This judgment is essential to adopting the optimum response for each circumstance. It cannot be substituted with rules and process. FBC is fully and completely dependent on the judgment of the members of the team and the willingness of the team and the institution to adhere to the boundary conditions set forth for the project. Within those boundaries the team must take ownership and responsibility for the job. The institution must empower the team to execute the mission and refrain from the temptation to control the project. Innovation must not only be tolerated, it must be encouraged. Clearly, the institution takes a risk in pursuing FBC, but the gains can be phenomenal, or the failures dismal, depending upon the skills of the team entrusted to do the job and the willingness of the institution to support them. FBC shows clearly that the people are an institutions most valuable resource.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] Other contributors to this paper include Dennis McCarthy, Bryan Fafaul, Richard Day, Richard Claffy, John Robinson, Ardeshir Azarbarzin, Mike Kelly from NASA Goddard Space Flight Center.
- [2] Robert A. Frosch, “A Classic Look at Systems Engineering,” Readings in Systems Engineering, edited by Francis T. Hoban and William M. Lawbaugh, NASA SP-6102. An edited version of this speech to the IEEE Group on Aerospace and Electronic Systems, IEEE’s International Convention, New York, March 26, 1969.
- [3] David Everett and Timothy Trenkle, “Robust Safing for Small, Low-Cost Satellites”, 9th Annual AIAA/USU Conference on Small Satellites, September 18-21, 1995.

8. BIOGRAPHY

Jim Watzin is currently the project manager for the NASA GSFC Small Explorer (SMEX) Project. This project develops low cost, quick reaction spacecraft in support of NASA's space science community. He has been with the project since its start in 1988 where he previously served as the Chief Systems Engineer. In that capacity he led the design and development of the initial three SMEX missions (SAMPEX, FAST, and SWAS). As Project Manager, he led the development efforts of the TRACE and WIRE mission teams.

The project has launched the four satellites and is beginning preparations for launching its 5th satellite, WIRE, in February of this year. The project is also completing the

prototyping of SMEX•Lite, a high technology, next generation spacecraft that will finish qualification testing in early 1999.

Mr. Watzin has been employed by NASA since 1980 and has a background in Attitude Control and Systems Engineering. He is the author of 15 technical papers originating from his work at GSFC. He earned a BS in Mechanical Engineering from the University of South Carolina and a MS in Dynamics and Control from the School of Aeronautics and Astronautics at Purdue University prior to working for NASA.

Recently, Mr. Watzin has been assigned the role of the Triana Project Manager. He will lead the development of this fast paced, innovative mission to an STS launch in late 2000 for a multi-year mission from the L1 libration point. Triana will provide real-time whole Earth observations to Earth science and educational organizations throughout the world.